

Synthesis and antimicrobial studies of 4-oxo-thiazolidine derivatives

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Abstract : Ethyl (4-chlorophenoxy)acetate (1) upon condensation with hydrazine hydrate gave 2-(4-chlorophenoxy)-acetohydrazide (2) which by condensation with aromatic aldehydes gave 2-(4-chlorophenoxy)-*N*-(substitutedbenzylidene)acetohydrazide (3a-k). Derivatives (3a-k) fused with thioglycolic acid and thiolactic acid gave 4-thiazolidinone derivatives (4a-k) and 5-methyl-4-thiazolidinone derivatives (5a-k) respectively. 4-Thiazolidinone derivatives (4a-k) treated with formaldehyde and *p*-fluoroaniline gave 2-(4-chlorophenoxy)-*N*-{2-(substitutedphenyl)-5-[(4-fluorophenyl)aminomethyl]-4-oxo-1,3-thiazolidine-3-yl}acetamide (6a-k). The structures of the synthesized compounds were assigned on the basis of IR, ¹H NMR, LC-MS and elemental analysis data.

Keywords : Cycloaddition, Schiff base's derivatives, Mannich reaction, thiazolidinones, microwave method, antimicrobial activity.

Introduction

The application of microwave irradiation is used for carrying out chemical transformations which are pollution free and economical^{1,2}. The microwave assisted reactions are more rapid, safe and with higher chemical yields, render the microwave method more superior to conventional method^{3,4}.

4-Thiazolidinone derivatives have various biological activities such as antibacterial, antifungal, anticonvulsant, anti-tubercular, anti-inflammatory, pesticidal, anticancer^{5,6}. Looking at the medicinal importance of 4-thiazolidinone derivatives, the present work reports the synthesis of some new 4-thiazolidinone derivatives.

Ethyl (4-chlorophenoxy)acetate (1) condensed with hydrazinehydrate gave 2-(4-chlorophenoxy)acetohydrazide^{7,8} (2) which on condensation with aromatic aldehydes gave 2-(4-chlorophenoxy)-*N*-(substitutedbenzylidene)acetohydrazide (3a-k). Derivatives (3a-k) fused with thioglycolic acid and thiolactic acid produces 4-thiazolidinone derivatives (4a-k) or 5-methyl-4-thiazolidinone derivatives (5a-k) respectively. 4-Thiazolidinone derivatives (4a-k) treated with formaldehyde and *p*-fluoroaniline gave 2-(4-chlorophenoxy)-*N*-{2-(substitutedphenyl)-5-[(4-

fluorophenyl)aminomethyl]-4-oxo-1,3-thiazolidine-3-yl}-acetamide (6a-k).

The structures of the synthesized compounds were assigned on the basis of IR, ¹H NMR, LC-MS and elemental analysis data.

All compounds were screened for antibacterial activity against *E. coli* and *S. aureus* using agar cup-borer⁹ method. The compounds were also screened for anti-fungal activity against *Fussarium moniliforme* and *Aspargillus niger* by food poisoning technique¹⁰

Results and discussion

All compounds were screened for antibacterial activity and anti-fungal activity. Some compounds had shown moderate activity. We have found that compounds gave good activity when substituted groups were halogen, hydroxy or alkoxy. All the observations are given in Table 2.

Experimental

All the melting points were determined in an open capillary method and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded in KBr on Buck M-500 spectrophotometer. ¹H

NMR spectra on a Bruker Advance OPX 200 MHz spectrophotometer with CDCl_3 as a solvent using TMS as internal reference and mass spectra (LC-MS) on a Perkin-Elmer API-165 instrument. Microwave assisted reactions were carried out in Samsung M183 DN and also in QPro-M microwave synthesis system with power output of 500 watts. The purity of the compounds was checked by TLC using silica gel-G.

Synthesis of 2-(4-chlorophenoxy)acetohydrazide⁷ 2 :

A mixture of ethyl (4-chlorophenoxy)acetate (19.85 g, 0.1 M) and hydrazine hydrate (20.0 g, 0.4 M) was refluxed in absolute ethanol for 2 h. The solution was cooled, poured into ice water, filtered and the resulting solid was recrystallised from aqueous ethanol, m.p. 122 °C.

Synthesis of 2-(4-chlorophenoxy)-N-(4-hydroxybenzylidene)acetohydrazide⁷ 3c :

Conventional method : A mixture of 2-(4-chlorophenoxy)acetohydrazide (2.00 g, 0.01 M) and 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde (1.49 g, 0.011 M) was refluxed in absolute ethanol for 3 h. The content was cooled, poured into ice water and treated with sodium bisulfite solution and then filtered. The crude product was recrystallised by ethanol.

Microwave method : A mixture of 2-(4-chlorophenoxy)acetohydrazide (2.00 g, 0.01 M) and 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde (1.49 g, 0.011 M) were taken in a conical flask and to it 10 ml ethanol was added and the mixture was placed inside a microwave oven for about 2–3 min. The content was cooled, poured into ice water and treated with sodium bisulfite solution, filtered. The crude product was recrystallised by ethanol, m.p. 225 °C.

IR (KBr) : 3405 (OH), 3097 (NH), 2984 (C–H str. sym.), 2964 (C–H str. asym.), 1691 (C=O), 1595 (C=N), 1259 (C–O–C), 731 cm^{-1} (C–Cl); mass spectra : 306.5 (M + 2 peak).

Similarly other compounds of the series were synthesized as above method (Table 1).

Synthesis of 2-(4-chlorophenoxy)-N-[2-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-4-oxo-1,3-thiazolidin-3-yl]acetamide⁷ 4c :

Conventional method : A mixture of 2-(4-chlorophenoxy)-N-(4-hydroxybenzylidene)acetohydrazide (3c) (3.04 g, 0.01 M) and thioglycolic acid (1.36 g, 0.015 M) were heated at 120–125 °C in oil bath for 12 h. The reaction mixture was cooled and treated with 10% NaHCO_3 solution. The product was isolated, filtered and recrystallized from aqueous methanol.

Microwave method : A mixture of 2-(4-chlorophenoxy)-N-(4-hydroxybenzylidene)acetohydrazide (3c) (3.04 g, 0.01 M) and thioglycolic acid (1.36 g, 0.015 M) were heated for 3 min. The content was cooled and then treated with sodium bicarbonate solution. The product was isolated and recrystallized by aqueous methanol, m.p. 180 °C.

IR (KBr) : 3400 (OH), 1710 (C=O), 1690 (C=O of 4-thiazolidinone ring), 1427 (C–N str.), 1236 (C–O–C), 707 (C–Cl), 655 cm^{-1} (C–S–C); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) : δ 4.1 (2H, s, CH_2 of 4-thiazolidinone ring), 4.5 (2H, s, CH_2 of CH_2CONH), 6.3 (1H, s, CH of 4-thiazolidinone ring), 6.7–8.2 (10H, m, Ar-H, NH, OR); mass spectra : 380.5 (M + 2 peak).

Similarly, other compounds of the series were synthesized (Table 1).

Synthesis of 2-(4-chlorophenoxy)-N-[2-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-5-methyl-4-oxo-1,3-thiazolidin-3-yl]acetamide⁷ 5c :

Conventional method : A mixture of 2-(4-chlorophenoxy)-N-(4-hydroxybenzylidene)acetohydrazide (3c) (3.04 g, 0.01 M) and thiolactic acid (1.59 g, 0.015 M) were heated at 120 °C in oil bath for 12 h. The content

Table 1. Physical and analytical data of compounds 3a-k, 4a-k, 5a-k and 6a-k

Code no.	R	Molecular formula	Mol. wt. (g/mol)	M.p. °C	yield %		Carbon (%)		Nitrogen (%)		Hydrogen (%)	
					Conv.	MW	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
3a	H	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{Cl}$	288.5	192	65	80	62.32	62.40	9.65	9.70	4.51	4.54
3b	2-Cl	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{Cl}_2$	323.0	142	66	82	55.68	55.75	8.62	8.67	3.71	3.74
3c	4-OH	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3\text{Cl}$	304.5	225	65	81	59.05	59.12	9.13	9.19	4.28	4.30
3d	2-OH	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3\text{Cl}$	304.5	199	64	80	59.05	59.12	9.13	9.19	4.28	4.30
3e	1-CH=CH	$\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{Cl}$	314.5	231	60	74	64.80	64.87	8.84	8.90	4.77	4.80
3f	4-OCH ₃	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3\text{Cl}$	318.5	178	67	83	60.21	60.29	8.72	8.79	4.71	4.74
3g	4-OH, 3-OCH ₃	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4\text{Cl}$	334.5	200	63	78	57.43	57.41	8.31	8.37	4.50	4.52
3h	3-Cl	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{Cl}_2$	323.0	188	62	75	55.67	55.75	8.62	8.67	3.71	3.74
3i	3-NO ₂	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_3\text{O}_4\text{Cl}$	333.5	182	59	72	53.91	53.98	12.52	12.59	3.60	3.62
3j	3-OH	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3\text{Cl}$	304.5	209	60	70	59.05	59.12	9.13	9.19	4.27	4.30

Note

Table-1 (contd.)

3k	3-OC ₆ H ₅	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₃ Cl	380.5	153	61	72	66.15	66.23	7.30	7.36	4.47	4.50
4a	H	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₃ SCl	362.5	Low	68	80	56.24	56.27	7.71	7.72	4.16	4.17
4b	2-Cl	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₃ SCl ₂	397.0	Low	69	82	51.38	51.40	7.04	7.05	3.54	3.55
4c	4-OH	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₄ SCl	378.5	180	67	81	53.89	53.90	7.38	7.39	3.98	3.99
4d	2-OH	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₄ SCl	378.5	105	68	80	53.89	53.90	7.38	7.39	3.98	3.99
4e	1-CH=CH	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₃ SCl	388.5	166	64	79	58.31	58.68	7.18	7.20	4.39	4.41
4f	4-OCH ₃	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₄ SCl	392.5	Low	69	83	55.01	55.03	7.12	7.13	4.34	4.36
4g	4-OH, 3-OCH ₃	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₅ SCl	408.5	113	66	78	52.87	52.88	6.84	6.85	4.18	4.19
4h	3-Cl	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₃ SCl ₂	397.0	Low	65	75	51.37	51.40	7.04	7.05	3.54	3.55
4i	3-NO ₂	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₃ O ₅ SCl	407.5	Low	64	72	50.05	50.07	10.29	10.30	3.44	3.46
4j	3-OH	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₄ SCl	378.5	Low	63	75	53.88	53.90	7.38	7.39	3.98	3.99
4k	3-OC ₆ H ₅	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₄ SCl	392.5	Low	64	72	55.01	55.03	7.12	7.13	4.35	4.36
5a	H	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₃ SCl	376.5	Low	67	80	57.29	57.37	7.38	7.43	4.52	4.55
5b	2-Cl	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₃ SCl ₂	411.0	Low	65	86	52.48	52.56	6.78	6.81	3.89	3.92
5c	4-OH	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₄ SCl	392.5	Low	67	81	54.03	55.03	7.10	7.13	4.33	4.36
5d	2-OH	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₄ SCl	392.5	Low	68	80	54.03	55.03	7.10	7.13	4.33	4.36
5e	1-CH=CH	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₃ SCl	402.5	Low	64	79	59.62	59.53	6.95	6.90	4.75	4.72
5f	4-OCH ₃	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₄ SCl	406.5	Low	69	83	56.00	56.09	6.83	6.88	4.68	4.71
5g	4-OH, 3-OCH ₃	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₅ SCl	422.5	Low	66	78	53.88	53.96	6.57	6.62	4.50	4.53
5h	3-Cl	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₃ SCl ₂	411.0	Low	65	75	52.48	52.56	6.76	6.81	3.89	3.92
5i	3-NO ₂	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₃ O ₅ SCl	421.5	Low	62	72	51.17	51.25	9.90	9.96	3.80	3.82
5j	3-OH	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₄ SCl	322.5	Low	63	75	54.95	55.03	7.07	7.13	4.33	4.36
5k	3-OC ₆ H ₅	C ₂₄ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₄ SCl	468.5	Low	64	72	61.39	61.47	5.91	5.97	4.48	4.51
6a	H	C ₂₄ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₃ SClF	485.5	Low	69	82	59.25	59.32	8.60	8.65	4.33	4.36
6b	2-Cl	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ N ₃ O ₃ SCl ₂ F	520.0	Low	67	84	55.31	55.39	8.02	8.07	3.84	3.87
6c	4-OH	C ₂₄ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₄ SClF	501.5	Low	69	83	57.35	57.43	8.32	8.37	4.20	4.22
6d	2-OH	C ₂₄ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₄ SClF	501.5	Low	68	82	57.35	57.43	8.32	8.37	4.20	4.22
6e	1-CH=CH	C ₂₆ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₃ SClF	511.5	Low	64	80	60.91	60.99	8.16	8.21	4.50	4.53
6f	4-OCH ₃	C ₂₅ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₄ SClF	515.5	Low	69	83	58.06	58.15	8.08	8.14	4.46	4.49
6g	4-OH, 3-OCH ₃	C ₂₅ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₅ SClF	531.5	Low	62	79	56.36	56.44	7.85	7.90	4.33	4.36
6h	3-Cl	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ N ₃ O ₃ SClF	520.0	Low	62	76	55.31	55.39	8.03	8.07	3.84	3.87
6i	3-NO ₂	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₅ SClF	530.5	Low	61	73	54.21	54.29	10.50	10.55	3.77	3.80
6j	3-OH	C ₂₄ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₄ SClF	501.5	Low	62	77	57.35	57.43	8.32	8.37	4.19	4.22
6k	3-OC ₆ H ₅	C ₃₀ H ₂₅ N ₃ O ₄ SClF	577.5	Low	64	75	62.25	62.33	7.22	7.27	4.13	4.36

Table 2. Antibacterial and antifungal activity of compounds 4a-k, 5a-k and 6a-k

Code no.	R	Zone of inhibition in mm		% of inhibition of growth	
		<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>A. niger</i>	<i>F. molani</i>
4a	H	6	16	32.57	30.58
4b	2-Cl	16	11	62.67	60.35
4c	4-OH	16	15	51.35	52.33
4d	2-OH	9	11	60.00	57.81
4e	1-CH=CH	9	11	54.21	51.37
4f	4-OCH ₃	8	15	55.71	50.06
4g	4-OH, 3-OCH ₃	12	12	52.34	48.20

Table-2 (contd.)

4h	3-Cl	10	17	64.50	59.68
4i	3-NO ₂	8	9	34.18	25.60
4j	3-OH	9	9	52.00	44.52
4k	3-OC ₆ H ₅	19	15	56.22	47.61
5a	H	10	13	35.01	38.21
5b	3-Cl	12	13	60.31	63.24
5c	4-OH	15	13	57.09	58.35
5d	2-OH	15	20	61.21	54.39
5e	1-CH=CH	10	10	39.55	40.09
5f	4-OCH ₃	12	13	58.49	65.00
5g	4-OH, 3-OCH ₃	9	9	48.38	45.64
5h	3-Cl	22	16	59.08	62.38
5i	3-NO ₂	10	9	27.01	30.00
5j	3-OH	16	14	40.22	52.36
5k	3-OC ₆ H ₅	14	13	59.22	58.61
6a	H	14	08	41.02	17.14
6b	2-Cl	13	05	51.39	55.47
6c	4-OH	09	09	57.50	51.07
6d	2-OH	10	07	42.59	47.21
6e	1-CH=CH	08	04	24.12	31.00
6f	4-OCH ₃	15	09	52.39	49.81
6g	4-OH, 3-OCH ₃	15	10	51.08	48.94
6h	3-Cl	16	09	48.26	60.24
6i	3-NO ₂	05	08	32.00	27.58
6j	3-OH	12	11	45.91	40.29
6k	3-OC ₆ H ₅	13	15	47.38	62.58
Std-1	Peniciline	22	21	-	-
Std-2	Tetracycline	20	20	-	-
Std-3	Norfloxacin	22	22	-	-
Std-4	Carbendazim	-	-	-	60.00
Std-5	Clotrimazole	-	-	75.00	-
Solvent	Methanol/DMF	-	-	-	-
Conc.	-	50 µg	50 µg	100 µg	100 µg

was cooled and then treated with sodium bicarbonate solution. The product was isolated and recrystallized by aqueous methanol.

Microwave method : A mixture of 2-(4-chlorophenoxy)-*N*-(4-hydroxybenzylidene)acetohydrazide (3.04 g, 0.01 *M*) and thiolactic acid (1.59 g, 0.015 *M*) were heated for 3 min. The content was cooled and then treated with sodium bicarbonate solution. The product was isolated and recrystallized by aqueous methanol.

IR (KBr) : 3409 (OH), 1695 (C=O), 1691 (C=O of 4-thiazolidinone ring), 1396 (C-N str.), 1247 (C-O-C), 754 (C-Cl), 692 cm⁻¹ (C-S-C); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ

1.7 (3H, d, *J* 3 Hz, CH-CH₃), 4.1 (1H, q, *J* 2 Hz, CH-CH₃), 4.3 (2H, s, CH₂CONH), 6.0 (1H, s, CH of 4-thiazolidinone ring), 6.7-8.2 (10H, m, Ar-H, NH, OH); mass spectra : 392.5 (*M* + 2 peak).

Similarly, other compounds of the series were synthesized (Table 1).

Synthesis of 2-(4-chlorophenoxy)-*N*-{2-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-5-[(4-fluorophenyl)aminomethyl]-4-oxo-1,3-thiazolidin-3-yl}acetamide¹¹ 6c :

Conventional method : To a solution of 2-(4-chlorophenoxy)-*N*-[2-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-4-oxo-1,3-thiazolidin-3-yl]acetamide (**4c**) (3.83 g, 0.01 *M*) in metha-

Note

Scheme 1

nol, methanal (0.6 g, 0.02 M) and *p*-fluoroaniline (2.22 g, 0.02 M) were added dropwise. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 2 h. The excess solvent was distilled off and poured into ice water. The solid thus obtained was filtered, washed with water and recrystallized from methanol.

Microwave method : 2-(4-Chlorophenoxy)-*N*-[2-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-4-oxo-1,3-thiazolidin-3-yl]acetamide (**4c**) (3.83 g, 0.01 M), methanal (0.6 g, 0.02 M) and *p*-fluoroaniline (2.22 g, 0.02 M) were taken in a conical flask and to it 10 ml of methanol was added and the

mixture was placed inside a microwave oven for about 2–3 min. The content was cooled and added into ice water. The solid thus obtained was filtered, washed with water and recrystallized from methanol.

IR (KBr) : 3596 (OH), 3219 (NH), 1713 (C=O), 1692 (C=O of 4-thiazolidinone ring), 1427 (C–N str), 1229 (C–O–C), 1026 (C–F), 696 (C–Cl), 640 cm^{-1} (C–S–C); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) : δ 3.4 (1H, t, J 2 Hz, CH-CH₂), 4.2 (2H, s, CH₂CONH), 6.0 (1H, s, CH of 4-thiazolidinone ring), 6.8–8.8 (17H, m, Ar-H, NH, CH-CH₂, OH); mass spectra : 505.5 (M + 4 peak).

Similarly, other compounds of the series were synthesized (Table 1).

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